

Community Service Programme on the Application of CRM (*Customer Relationship Management*) To Fishermen Group Partners Pt. Xyz

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Abstract:- Community Service Programme on the Application of CRM (Customer Relationship Management) to Fishermen Group Partners. Community service is an initiative that aims to advance and benefit a specific group of people. In this context, we developed a community service programme for fishermen group partners with a focus on the application of CRM (Customer Relationship Management) to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of their relationships with customers and other stakeholders. CRM is a strategic approach that can help improve the interaction and collaboration between companies or fishing groups and their customers. This programme aims to: Increase the awareness of fishing groups on the importance of CRM in improving relationships with their customers, Provide training and technical support to fishing groups in implementing effective CRM practices, Assist fishing groups in identifying new opportunities, managing customer databases, and improving their services, Improve the ability of fishing groups to listen to customer feedback, respond to complaints, and build long-term relationships. Through close cooperation with the fishing groups, the programme aims to deliver tangible benefits, such as increased sales of their fish, improved brand reputation, and improved service quality. By implementing CRM, fishermen groups are expected to better understand their customers' needs, maintain ongoing relationships, and better respond to market changes. This service programme also includes continuous monitoring and evaluation to measure its impact and success. As such, the programme has the potential to provide long-term benefits to the fishing

groups, their customers, and the local community as a whole.

Keywords:- Fishing Group Partners, Customer Relationship Management, Fishing Group Partner Satisfaction, Fishing Group Partner Needs,

I. INTRODUCTION

Improving Macroeconomic growth Today's business development depends not only on the quality of the product, but also on the quality of the service, which further encourages fishermen group partners to buy the product or use the solution offered. This does not mean that the products marketed can be of poor quality, especially if the products offered have more or less the same competitors. It is different for products that are essentially unique, high quality and have strong differentiation, so that fishermen group partners will have a clear value, even though there are similar products (Surya et al, 2021; Garcia-Muiña, González-Sánchez, Ferrari & Settembre-Blundo, 2018; Kabir, 2019; Dhahri, Slimani & Omri, 2021).

Service quality remains very important in dealing with fishermen group partners who require a high level of excellence. High-quality service means being able to provide harmony with the needs of fishermen group partners. Essentially, both upper, middle and even lower-class fishermen group partners need good and quality service, it's just that the levels are different (Gupta & Singh, 2020; Legenvre & Gualandris, 2018; Hicks et al, 2019; Sunder & Antony, 2018; Pascual-Fernández et al, 2019).

If observed, the core of the current competition is more on how PT XYZ company realises who its target market is, how high the quality of its products is. Equally important is how high value it is able to provide to fishing group partners and how it treats fishing group partners from day to day. Through CRM (*Customer Relationship Management*), PT. XYZ can find out more about how far to utilise CRM in current business ventures and how companies can increase their sales and know their fishing group partners better, so that they can serve them better.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Yahya (2008: 82) Customer Relationship Management is a comprehensive business strategy in a company that allows the company to effectively manage relationships with fishing group partners. Thus, through Customer Relationship Management the company can approach so as to draw some information about the needs and desires of fishing group partners (Guerola-Navarro et al,2021; Deszczyński, 2018; Cho, Edebie, Lau & Hong, 2020).

Based on the above understanding, the researcher concludes that Customer Relationship Management is a comprehensive company management concept that focuses on fishing group partners as the main factor in order to increase the competitive advantage between companies and aims to obtain maximum satisfaction of fishing group partners, which of course will bring benefits to the company at a relatively cheaper cost (Marolt, Zimmermann, Žnidaršič & Pucihar, 2020; Lerbinger, 2018; Kitchens, Dobolyi, Li & Abbasi, 2018).

Focusing on fishing group partners is the key to achieving sustainable competitive advantage in today's business competition. Competitive advantage with a focus on fisher group partners can be achieved by knowing information about who their fisher group partners are, what their fisher group partners want, how their fisher group partners' needs are satisfied and other related factors (Dijkstra, van Beukering & Brouwer, 2021; Hawkins & Hoon, 2019).

CRM is a strategy on how to optimise profitability through developing fisher group partner satisfaction. CRM is a strategy that focuses on all things related to the focus on fishing group partners. CRM is the process of acquiring, retaining and developing profitable customers. According to Newell quoted by Kartika Imasari, Customer Relationship Management (CRM) is a modification and learning of consumer behaviour every time from every interaction, treatment of fishing group partners and building strength between consumers and companies (Moser & Moser, 2021; Gil-Gomez, Guerola-Navarro, Oltra-Badenes & Lozano-Quilis, 2020).

According to Kotler and Keller, CRM or fisher group partner relationship management is the process of managing detailed information about each fisher group partner. CRM manages all "touchpoints" of fisher group partners to maximise fisher group partner loyalty. Contact points of fisher group partners are all events where fisher group partners come into contact with products or services, ranging from personal experience, mass communication to casual observation (Al-Dmour & Hayat, 2019; Shivani, 2019; Kumar, 2018).

III. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Purpose

- Objective: Foster relationships with fishing group partners to increase company profits Use complete information to provide satisfactory service Support the process of repeat sales to fishing group partners.

B. Benefits

- Benefits: Increased number of fishermen group partners, i.e. finding new fishermen group partners while maintaining the satisfaction level of existing fishermen group partners.
- Knowing the level of company ownership in fishing group partners, namely by knowing the needs of fishing group partners. Knowing the needs of fishing group partners in the future, namely through the results of transactions that have been carried out and from the results of the analysis of transaction data that has been collected.
- Knowing the abnormality in every transaction activity, namely knowing criminal acts such as fraud and so on.
- Knowing the improvements that must be made to the services provided to fishing group partners.
- Able to analyse transaction data patterns, for example being able to know the combination of products that will be sold at certain times.
- Reduce operational risk by knowing what to expect and what has gone wrong through the history of the fishermen group partners.

In writing this journal, the formulation is expressed as follows:

- Why is CRM important in the company PT XYZ at this time?
- How to implement CRM in order to increase the satisfaction and needs of fishermen group partners are maintained and continue to increase?

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

The method used is descriptive analysis, to analyse the problems faced by a business venture during the period January to June 2023 so that a broad and in- depth picture is obtained. In this study, the type of data used is primary data. Instruments for data collection are obtained directly from observations in the field, namely by interviewing with PT. XYZ Fisherman partners.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There are three stages of CRM, namely (Kalakota and Robinson 2001):

- Acquire new fishermen group partners (acquire). New fishermen group partners are acquired by providing easy access to information, new innovations, and attractive services.
- Improve relationships with existing fishermen group partners (enhance). The company tries to establish relationships with fishing group partners by providing good service to its fishing group partners (customer service). The application of cross selling or up selling in the second stage can increase the company's revenue and reduce the cost of acquiring fishing group partners (reduce cost).
- Retaining fishermen group partners. This stage is an effort to gain the loyalty of fishing group partners by listening to fishing group partners and trying to fulfil the wishes of fishing group partners.

According to Laudon and Traver 2002, CRM stores fishermen group partner information and records all contacts that occur between fishermen group partners and companies, and creates fishermen group partner profiles for company staff who need information about the fishermen group partners.

The definition according to Kotler 2003, CRM supports a company to provide services to fishing group partners in real time and establish relationships with each fishing group partner through the use of information about fishing group partners.

A. CRM Classification

Applications that implement CRM are classified into two (Dyche 2002), namely: Operational CRM Operational CRM is known as the "front office" of the company. This CRM application plays a role in the interaction with fishing group partners. Operational CRM includes an integrated automation process of the entire business process, such as marketing, sales, and service automation. One of the CRM applications included in the operational CRM category. Through CRM applications, a company can provide

services to fishing group partners.

Some examples of services include (Greenberg 2002 in Turban et al. 2004: Providing product search. Fishing group partners often have difficulty in finding the product they want, so a search facility is needed. Providing free products or services, something that can attract fishing group partners to visit the web is the availability of free products or services. Providing services or information about product use. Providing online ordering. Provide booking status information facility.

B. CRM Analytics

Analytical CRM is known as the "back office" of the company. This CRM application plays a role in understanding the needs of fisher group partners. Analytical CRM plays a role in carrying out fisher group partner and market analysis, such as market trend analysis and fisher group partner behaviour analysis. The data used in Analytical CRM is data derived from Operational CRM.

In general, the implementation of the CRM concept emphasises the use of information technology as a strategy to create relationships with fishermen group partners. The emergence of CRM as an alternative solution in managing fishermen group Partner Relationships is generally triggered by several consequences of the development of the company's strategic environment, namely:

A new paradigm shift from transactional marketing to relationship marketing, a transition in the development of the company's organisational structure from function-oriented to process-oriented. There is an understanding that a proactive approach is better relative to a reactive one. Utilisation of information technology capabilities in maximising the value of fishermen group partners. It is believed that fishermen group partners are not only the company's partners but also the company's business assets.

C. CRM Concept

Customer Relationship Management (CRM) has become a buzz term in recent years. Coupled with the development of information technology that increasingly adds various business applications, CRM has become one of the interesting business processes to be discussed. Customer Relationship Management covers all aspects related to a company's interaction with its fishing group partners. This can be in the form of selling services or goods. It all starts with marketing activities towards fishermen group partners. Marketing activities manage all aspects of the fishermen group partner life cycle, from sales, acquisition, fulfilment, to retention, as shown in Figure 1 below:

Fig 1 CRM Activities

➤ Stages of using CRM (Customer Relationship Management)

Customer Relationship Management (CRM) is one of the e-commerce developments that allow companies to develop closer relationships with fishing group partners where companies can learn and provide service options that match the demands of fishing group partners. The following are the stages of using Customer Relationship Management (CRM), among others:

Acquire new fishermen group partners (acquire), by promoting the advantages of products or services in terms of innovation and convenience because the value of a service for fishermen group partners is a better product and supported by satisfying services.

Increase the profitability of existing fishing group partners. (Enhance the profitability of existing group fishery partners by encouraging competition and better sales of fish owned by group fishery partners. Retain profitable group fishery partners, by offering what the specific group fishery partners need rather than what the market group fishery partners need, as the value to group fishery partners is the proactive value that best suits their needs.

The company's current focus is on how to maintain existing fishermen group partners that are sure to provide benefits to the company rather than how to get new fishermen group partners that are not necessarily profitable.

➤ Benefits of Using CRM Applications

Increase Loyalty of Fishing Group Partners CRM applications use information from all points of contact with fishing group partners, whether via the web, call centre, or through marketing and service staff in the field. The consistency and accessibility of this information enables better sales and service with important information about the fisher group partners.

Reducing Costs, CRM also enables lower cost sales or services in a specific and focused marketing programme. Targeted to the right fishing group partner at the right time.

Improve Operational Efficiency, Automation of a company's sales and service processes can reduce the risk of service quality deterioration and reduce cash flow burden. The use of web technology and call centres, for example, will reduce bureaucratic barriers and administrative costs and processes that may arise.

Improved Time to Market, the app brings products to market faster with better information on fishermen group partners, trend data on purchases by fishermen group partners.

Revenue Enhancement, the app provides information to increase revenue and profits. With the app, companies can conduct sales and services through the website, enabling global sales opportunities without the need for specialised efforts to support sales and services.

➤ Critical Steps to Improving CRM Strategy

Important steps to enhance an effective CRM strategy include:

- Identify the characteristics of each fishermen group partner.
- Modelling the value of each fishing group partner segment.
- Create proactive strategies and implementation plans or business methods that address the needs of fisher group partners, starting with the most potential fisher group partner segments.
- Redesigned the company structure along with the work process, technology and reward system for fisher group partners in order to implement the strategy of improving relationships with fisher group partners.

D. Customer Relationship Management (CRM) Concepts and Activities

Customer relationship management is a corporate-level strategy, which focuses on building and maintaining relationships with fishing group partners. Several software packages are available with different approaches to CRM. However, CRM is not a technology per se, but a holistic approach to organizational philosophy, which emphasises close relationships with fishing group partners. CRM takes care of the organisation's philosophy at all levels, including policies and processes, customer service, employee training, marketing, fund management systems and information. CRM systems integrate marketing, sales, and customer service from end-to-end.

The concept of using Customer Relationship Management (CRM) is to know, know and explore what is expected from a fishing group partner or consumer of a company. With Customer Relationship Management (CRM), the company can build a database of fishing group partners, which will record the profile of fishing group partners such as type of preference, occupation and amount of income. This information will be used to build a relationship between the company and fishing group partners, in addition to between fishing group partners with each other.

The things that companies engaged in the sale of fish do by using Customer Relationship Management (CRM) in their daily activities are:

- Customers enquire either over the phone or by coming in person and asking about fish products.
- The availability of fish displays in several ponds for service to fishing group partners is prioritised and always serves well in terms of providing all the needs needed by fishing group partners.
- Its trading company application used by the company on line, will show in real time can facilitate fishermen group partners in the process of creating sales, and can even increase revenue.

E. Added Value in using CRM

The use of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) in the tourism sector in their business activities provides an advantage or value for the company, this value is the benefit that the company gets on the use of Customer Relationship Management (CRM). Customer Relationship Management (CRM) helps the company in collecting and analysing information about the history of fishing group partners, what are the pleasures, what are the complaints and even other data to predict what the fishing group partners will want in the future.

In addition, Customer Relationship Management (CRM) helps companies to develop their business based on complete knowledge of the desires of fishing group partners, market dynamics and competition in a way:

Offering higher status of fisher group partners (gold card vs silver card) Identifying fisher group partners' wishes to avoid fraud Reducing operational risk as fisher group partners' data is stored in a system Faster response to fisher

group partners.

F. Implementation of PT XYZ Company using CRM

The company uses Customer Relationship Management (CRM) applications for several reasons including for on-line booking problems so that fishing group partners do not need to come directly to the company, product ordering, fishing group partners do not need to come directly to buy products but can use on-line ordering methods and can choose the preferred product, price, and payment by credit card or transfer, etc. so that this CRM application is very useful for fishing group partners.

In addition, the use of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) in the PT XYZ company can be expected that communication with fishing group partners and prospective fishing group partners is more varied. So that the use of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) can increase the sales of trading companies such as this fish farming. With internet-based communication media with this technological sophistication, a company can increase its company value and develop along with the times.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Acquire new fishermen group partners (acquire). New fishermen group partners are acquired by providing easy access to information, new innovations, and attractive services.

Improve relationships with existing fishermen group partners (enhance). The company seeks to build relationships with its fishermen group partners by providing good customer service.

Retaining fishermen group partners. This stage is an effort to gain the loyalty of fishing group partners by listening to fishing group partners and trying to fulfil the wishes of fishing group partners.

VII. IMPLICATION MANAGERIAL

Research on the application of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) to PT XYZ's fishermen group partners in community service programmes can make a significant contribution to various stakeholders, including governments, communities and schools.

This research can help the government in its efforts to improve the welfare of the fishing community. By implementing CRM, fishermen can increase their operational efficiency, improve product quality, and access a wider market and Increased productivity and quality of fishermen products can contribute to local economic growth, which will benefit the local government.

The fishermen will directly benefit from the implementation of CRM. By strengthening relationships with their buyers and consumers, they can increase their income. The implementation of CRM may require increased knowledge and skills among fishermen. This research can

provide the necessary training and education to improve their competence in customer relationship management.

This research can also serve as an example for other fishing communities in different regions to implement CRM practices in their businesses. This could have a broader positive impact on the fisheries sector in Indonesia, helping to reduce uncertainty and improve the sustainability of marine resources, as well as improving the lives of fishers overall.

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